

TEENAGE GIRLS' RANGE OF MODERN DRESSES.

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Annotation: *The article analyzing the range of clothes for teenage girls, the collection of world brands, it is about the offer to produce clothes that are specific and suitable for our mentality.*

Keywords: *Modern fashion, fashion features, global brands, modern clothing styles, innovation, design, model, fabric, clothing indicators, clothing demand, monochromatic.*

With a wide range of features in the field of modern fashion clothing, we have studied the range of teenage girls' dresses presented in fashion shows and magazines by world fashion designers. Fashionable teenage girls dresses come in a variety of styles, models and materials[4]. Fashion, of course, exists in many areas of human activity, such as changing patterns of cultural heritage, but primarily fashion helps us shape our appearance. Modern man, on the one hand, prefers high-quality, simplest, comfortable clothes, on the other hand, he wants to emphasize his uniqueness and ability to express himself. an attempt to search for the future or unknown forms; non-traditional form solutions are chosen. Therefore, most of the designers use innovative and natural materials, modelers try new forms and previous forms, thus creating new projects, that is, such experiments have high results in the direction of fashion. Design is one of the most subjective things in the world. Everyone considers the perception of form and color at the psychophysical level, and this perception is what the author emphasizes[2].

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what the author emphasizes. We analyzed the fashion trends of teenage girls' dresses for 2021-2022. Girls are distinguished by their interest in beautiful and bright, unusual clothes and things. These indicators are very relevant. It reflects the social needs of the consumer. From a girl's point of view, colors, shapes and everything else satisfy all her social needs. From morning to evening, he shows his appearance [7]. What will be the most modern trends on dresses in the new season 2021-2022. [Appendix 1-2] The most fashionable dresses of the 2021-2022 season, presented by leading brands and couturiers, allow teenage girls to look romantic, street style and casual. Modern teenage girls love the ensemble of dresses in the fashion world as well as sports and casual style. Teenage girls' dresses are mainly bright colors, bright pink, green and yellow colors. In the winter season and spring-autumn seasons, teenage girls are offered "oversize" styles, different bright colors, of course, their complexity and increases its elegance. These dresses are combined with their bright colors, ultra-bright colors, black colors and red colors with a very strict style[2]. Modern teenage clothes are complex and diverse. Being an object of mass production, it must meet many requirements that determine the technical and economic characteristics of human consumption. A teenage girl's dress should be aesthetically pleasing and comfortable. The shirt is intended for daily use, resistant to friction, waterproof and should not cause allergies in people. A fashionable dress has always been the choice of real girls who want to show delicate and sophisticated images with favorite accessories in any season, especially for the warm spring-autumn period. In fashion, most girls worry about their perfect appearance in the warm season, because appearance plays an important role for teenagers. The choice of materials for clothing is developed taking into account the design features of the proposed model, consumer and production demand, as well as the variety of manufactured materials and accessories[6]. Modern fabric production techniques allow to obtain interesting textures, optimal finishing effects and artistic color design, therefore, the produced spring-autumn seasonal dresses significantly expand.

There are different types of materials in the present era, from natural fiber to synthetic fiber materials, 70% natural or 30% viscose fiber to higher materials should be used. Depending on the physical and mechanical properties, such materials are considered to have low heat storage properties and high air permeability[1].

Children's and teenagers' clothes prepared by designers are full of characters of cartoons and comics. Jacquard fabrics and jacquard imitation prints have become a fashion trend in the youth collection. Monochromatic things in collections for teenagers are not less than their position, the main thing is that they are combined with each other and complement the image. Fashion starts with teenagers. Teen fashion is inspired by the representatives of the upper class, they dare to wear bright, surprising clothes and are not afraid to challenge passers-by on the street[4]. Without the right to monotony and monotony, to stand out from others, to feel free, to emphasize unity with friends and their environment - these are the slogans of young designers and fashion designers. Designers rely on dynamism, maximum comfort and stiffness in movements when creating clothing collections for teenagers for the spring-summer-autumn season. Designers struggle to find a compromise between the conflicting desires of young customers, but solving a difficult task sometimes leads to the creation of interesting, modern teenage clothes. A sophisticated image for teenage girls is a chiffon or guipure blouse with jeans and clearly romantic style accessories[7].

The table below shows the analysis of the jacket of the world's brands for teenage girls..

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Clothing nami	Appearance and silhouette	Brand type	Color gamut
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<p>“Seasonal black crow” imitation</p>	<p>Dolce & Gabbana</p>	<p>Dolce & Gabbana</p>	<p>Seasonal clothes from black knitted fabrics</p>
<p>a girl's shirt with a shoulder-V</p>		<p>LIU JO</p>	<p>Floral print spring-summer girl's shirt.</p>
<p>COSE P.A.R.O.S.H.</p>	<p>P.A.R.O.S.H.</p>	<p>P.A.R.O.S.H.</p>	<p>Floral print girl's dress in lilac color.</p>
<p>STILE XIPPI</p>	<p>Christian Dior</p>	<p>CHRISTIAN DIOR</p>	<p>Bakhrama noodles in hippie style</p>

<p>Iron cloth</p>		<p>Gucci</p>	<p>Puffed sleeves, wide cuffs, small stand-up collar</p>
<p>Sports style</p>		<p>ZARA</p>	<p>“NEW IN KIDS” 2022- special collection for the day special from sidan</p>
<p>Prinsessa</p>		<p>Tonerna</p>	<p>Summer jacket for teenage girls</p>

<p>shirt</p>		<p>Peseriko</p>	<p>Study and meeting for teenage girls for shirt</p>
<p>Tonerna</p>		<p>Chinese brand</p>	<p>Long sleeve teenage girl's dress for fall season</p>
<p>Summer-2021</p>		<p>Carolina Herrera</p>	<p>High waist, wide skirt, stand collar, drapery skirt, scarf, maxi length, cut out, floral print.</p>

<p>Summer- 2021</p>			<p>VAKKO Turkish brand</p>	<p>Bright green natural mat girl's dress in a romantic style</p>
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The development of the clothing industry in Uzbekistan has taken a significant step forward for several years. These are reflected in the increase of small production enterprises, having their own brands, advertising services, etc[2]. The article talks about how teenagers and children's fashion has changed in recent years and what fashion clothes to choose. Based on the above-mentioned ideas and qualities, the main goal of production enterprises is to produce clothes that match our mentality[3].

REFERENCES

- [1].S.SH.Tashpolatov, M.K.Ramazanova, G.G'.Alimova, SH.G'.Jo'rayeva "Designing, modeling and artistically decorating a wide range of clothes" – Tashkent: Faylasuf, 2013.
- [2]. Tursunova, X.Sh., Mamatqulova Saida Rahmatovna. (2020). Ayollar paltosi uchun gazlamalar taxlili. 3 rd international congress of the human and social science researches (itobiad).
- [3]. F.Abdullayeva "Technology of sewing children's clothes" Toshkent:2006
- [4]. Analysis of the development of older women's clothing of different subcultures (On the example of muslim women's clothing) SM Husanqizi, YD Ubaydulloyevna, HJ Valiyevich - Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 2021
- [5].Asian Journal of Multi dimensional Research (ADouble Blind Refereed& Peer Reviewed International Journal)DOI: WAYS TO SOLVE PROBLEMS IN THE

PRODUCTION OF KNIT WEAR M. M. Ulugboboyeva*; X.Sh.Tursunova**

<http://tarj.in/images/download/ajmr/AJMR-SEPTEMBER-2021-FULL-JOURNAL.pdf>

[6]. ANALYSIS OF WOMEN'S CLOTHES SEWING - A STUDY TO DEVELOP A NORM OF TIME SPENT ON THE TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF KNITTING PRODUCTION

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<https://sciencebring.com/index.php/ijasr/article/view/31>

<https://doi.org/10.37547/ijasr-02-03-03>

[7]. Nizamova, B. B., & Mamatqulova, S. R. (2021). Analysis of the Range Of Modern Women's Coats. The American Journal of Engineering and Technology, 3(9), 18-23.